

Emergence of nonlinear times and GUP by decaying quantum holes in biological systems-a hypothesis

Abstract:

Introduction:

The Urey-Miller experiments from one side and the Montagnier group's results from other side show that waves may induce life molecules in liquids. However, the question arises that why many other labs couldn't re-obtain these results? We open a discussion about the existence of new life holes which may be detected more by chance. These holes have some special signatures like time loop.

Aim:

We explore the signature of quantum holes near biological cells

Method:

1. We cut a leaf into several parts and produce many small pores in them.
2. We put them on a metal-glass slide near a 1000x microscope.
3. We connect this slide to a heater from one side and a cooler from other side such as temperature could be changed very fast.
4. We put an electrical system for applying intense waves with different frequencies near this slide.
5. We use of some chemical matters including carbon, nitrogen, water and hydrogen.
6. We apply sudden changes in waves and temperature and take video .
7. We repeat above stages for bird embryonic heart and vessels.
8. Bird heart should be alive and blood vessels should work

Results:

1. In some experiments, we observe that some scenes are repeating. For example, a scene of motions of molecules in two very separated times is

repeating. Although, there are some minor differences in scenes so. It seems that under some conditions, life holes decay and some time loops or nonlinear times are appeared.

2. In these experiments, the relation between time and energy in a generalized uncertainty principle includes higher orders of time.
3. Minor differences in scenes may be due to odd orders of time in non-linear system.
4. By changing space-time, some molecules disappear and some new molecules appear. This event is repeating for a period of time.

Conclusion:

In above experiments, it seems that by decaying life holes, GUP is emerged and time is looped. It means that GUP relations includes higher orders of time and consequently, time goes and returns. Now, the question arises that what is the origin of these wonderful effects and holes ? To response, we should consider the nature of bio-cosmos more carefully. Up to date, the relation between the origin of life and cosmos was less under considerations. Recently, Abraham Loeb has argued that in one of stages after big bang, temperature of universe was between 273-373 K and initial life molecules were emerged. Maybe, these molecules form initial cosmic clouds which decay into small parts. Then, these small clouds surrounded by molecules and form present planets. These life clouds were under hard pressures and according to conservation law, some of their matters convert to energy and built life holes with the memory of life molecules. On other hand, some other holes may come from extra dimensions. Because, in string theory, we have some branes in extra dimensions which may have life molecules. These molecules also may be under pressure and some of them change to holes. Both of holes are emerged under intense gravity and may obey of generalized uncertainty principle and non-linear time. For this reason, by their decay, time could be looped. These holes could be detected only by cells. Because, DNAs within cells are built from compacted spinors which their pressures change the space-time. These changes in medium provide good conditions for absorbing quantum holes. Number of these life holes may be a constant. Consequently, number of life molecules should be a constant and by increasing number of creatures, their sizes and number of

molecules should decrease. For this reason, initial dinosaurs convert to present animals.

Keywords: GUP; Nonlinear time; Quantum hole; biological systems

I.Introduction:

Recently, some wonderful results have been published which generated many discussions in scientific groups. First results have been proposed by Urey and Miller. They have claimed that by using waves and some chemical molecules, induced life molecules like amino acids in water container [1,2]. Second results have been proposed by Montagnier group. They have claimed that if we put two vessels, one including water and virus and other including pure water within a coil and connected it to a generator, signatures of virus could be induced in pure water [3,4]. Many other groups have tried to re-obtain their results, however, most of them couldn't. The question arises that why these results could be obtained by chance. Maybe response is the existence of hidden parameters, for example, a type of waves which couldn't be detected always. We can call these new waves as quantum life holes. Maybe, one ask about the origin of these waves. To answer, we should reconsider the origin of life and cosmos in bio-cosmos theory. Because, these holes may be appeared during evolutions of bio-cosmos. The best model for bio-cosmos has been proposed by Abraham Loeb [5,6]. He shows that at initial stages after big bang, temperature of universe reduced to 273-373 K which was the best condition for production of life molecules. Maybe, first, these molecules were formed and then, under some conditions like the pressure, they convert to energy and life holes. In this paper, we want to explore these life holes. We will show that by decaying these holes, time is looped and GUP is emerged. Previously, the shape of GUP was [7,8]:

$$\Delta p \Delta x > \hbar [(1 + c(\Delta p)^2 + c \langle p \rangle^2) + 2c_i(1 + (\Delta p_i)^2 + \langle p_i \rangle^2)]$$

We generalize above equation by replacing time and energy and write:

$$\Delta t \Delta E > \hbar [(1 + c(\Delta t)^2 + c \langle t \rangle^2) + 2c_i(1 + (\Delta t_i)^2 + \langle t_i \rangle^2)] + \dots$$

Above relation shows that time and energy have non-linear relations and some loops may occur. We will show that these loops may be signatures of life holes.

II. Theoretical Model:

In this research, we propose a model to consider the origin of quantum holes, life and cosmos altogether. This model introduces some new quantum holes which could decay to life matters and produce viruses, bacteria, animals and plants. We consider methods for detecting these quantum holes and their effects.

A: The energy-Matter conservation law:

To consider the origin of quantum holes, life and cosmos, we need to remember the energy matter conservation law and its applications. We have:

$$E = M C^2$$

Where E is the energy, M is the mass and C is the velocity of light.

According to this law, near heavy atoms, some waves like photons could convert to matters like electrons and positrons.

$$E \leftrightarrow e^- + e^+$$

Also, these particles could couple, vanish and some photons are emerged. We will show that the same event occurs during the emergence of life. Some quantum holes could convert to life molecules like proteins, DNAs, RNAs, carbons, viruses and others (See Figure 1).

B: The process of formation of life clouds and their explosions in Abraham Loeb theory

Now, the question arises that what is the origin of life holes. To answer, we should have a review on process of formation of present bio-cosmos. According to Abraham Loeb theory, after big bang, first particles were emerged. These particles joined to each other and built atoms. When, temperature of universe was around 273-373 K, atoms joined to each other and formed molecules like carbon dioxide, water molecules, amino acids, and maybe DNA/RNAs or at least their bases. These molecules formed first and initial life clouds. These clouds divided into many parts which each part may be surrounded by other molecules and form present stars and planets (See Figure 2). These small clouds could emit life holes.

C: Bio-cosmos in string theory

In string theory, all particles are replaced by strings. Also, our universe is located on a brane which is a 3+1 dimensional page. This page moves in 11 dimensional world and interacts with other branes. Maybe, some types of life molecules are existed on other branes which send life holes toward our brane. Thus, origin of some creatures and life molecules may be other branes in extra dimensions (See Figure 3).

C: Emergence of life by quantum holes in 11 dimensional world:

According to conservation law, quantum holes which come from the branes in extra dimensions and life clouds within the center of planets convert to life molecules, viruses, bacteria, animals and plants. Maybe, first, viruses were emerged and they joined to each other and built bacteria. Then, bacteria evolves and form single celled creatures. Next, these cells join each other and form big animals and plants. In fact, there is a relation between number of quantum holes and creatures:

Number of quantum holes = number of creatures \otimes number of their life molecules

If one supposes that number of quantum holes is a constant, thus, by increasing number of creatures, their sizes should be reduced such as number of their molecules decreases (See Figure 4). For this reason, initial dinosaurs convert to present animals like birds.

D: GUP and non-linear time within biological systems:

Maybe this question arises that how we could detect quantum holes? To response this question, we should describe events that may occur by decaying life holes. We know that nature lets us to measure a small in energy in a very small period of time. This is known as Uncertainty Principle:

$$\Delta E \Delta t > \hbar$$

Where E is energy, t is time and \hbar is the Planck constant. When a quantum hole is trapped by our detectors, in fact, we measure a change in energy in a period of time. Above relation describes a dependency between energy of holes and needed time to measure it. This time should be very small as above equation indicates. However, in some conditions, we have more time. For example, when, pressure increases, above principle could be generalized. Up to date, Generalized Uncertainty Principle has been known that have extra terms:

$$\Delta E \Delta t > \hbar G (\Delta E, \Delta t)$$

Where G is a function of time and energy. It could be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} G (\Delta E, \Delta t) = & [(1 + c(\Delta t)^2 + c \langle t \rangle^2) \\ & + 2c_i(1 + (\Delta t_i)^2 + \langle t_i \rangle^2) \\ & + 2b_i(1 + (\Delta t_i)^3 + \langle t_i \rangle^3) \\ & + (1 + c'(\Delta E)^2 + c \langle E' \rangle^2) \\ & + 2c'_i(1 + (\Delta E_i)^2 + \langle E_i \rangle^2) \\ & + 2b'_i(1 + (\Delta E_i)^3 + \langle E_i \rangle^3)] + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Where coefficients depend on pressures and energies. Above equation shows that under some conditions, time and energy could have non-linear relations. For example, under the pressures within the center of earth or other branes in extra compacted dimensions, matters disappeared and some holes are emerged which obey from non-linear relations between time and energy and consequently, by their decay, we will have non-linear time. It means that time goes and returns like an oscillations, however, because of third and other odd orders of time, size of time loops and events interior them could be different (See Figure 5).

E: Biological cells emit quantum holes

We know that each DNA is built from many charged particles. Specially, they are built from electrons and atoms which have spins. According to Pauli exclusion principle, parallel electrons repel each other. Within a nucleus, many parallel spins of genetic matters of a DNA become close to each other and a huge negative pressure is emerged. We have:

$$\Delta P < 0 \text{ or } \Delta P > 0 \rightarrow \Delta E < 0 \text{ or } \Delta E > 0 \rightarrow GUP \rightarrow \Delta t < 0 \text{ or } \Delta t > 0$$

Above equation shows that huge pressures and energies produce non-linear time holes. These holes could come out and decay and consequently, some time loops may be emerged (See Figure 6).

E: Previous observations:

Recently, two experiments have been done which shown the production of biological matters by waves.

1. **The Urey-Miller Experiment:** In this experiment, water in one container becomes hot, evaporates and its molecules enter into other container. In second container, we have two electrodes which are connected to a generator, some CH_4 , NH_3 and some other molecules. Electrodes produce currents and waves and system eventually, become cooled. In cooled water, one can detect amino acids and some other molecules of life (See Figure 7). In this experiment, quantum holes which are emitted by the earth core or branes could be trapped and according to conservation law converts to life molecules.
2. **The Montagnier Experiment:** Group of Montagnier built a coil and put two vessels, one including water and viruses and other pure in it. Then, they connect this coil to a generator. In these conditions, life holes could be trapped, take shape of viruses and decay in other pure water. For this reason, one can detect viruses in other container by PCR (See Figure 8).

Figure 1: Near heavy atoms, photons and waves could convert to matters like electron-positron and reversely, these particles could annihilate and photons are emerged(a hypothesis)

Figure 2: The process of formation of life molecules and cosmos in a unified bio-cosmos theory(a hypothesis)

Figure 3: Our universe is located on a brane which is connected to other brane in extra dimensions(a hypothesis)

Figure 4. Quantum holes which are radiating from life clouds and branes convert to viruses, bacteria and then animals and plants. (a hypothesis)

Figure 5: According to GUP, quantum holes could decay and sometime loops are emerged. (a hypothesis)

$$\Delta t \Delta E > \hbar [(1 + c (\Delta t)^2 + \langle t \rangle^2) + 2 c_i ((\Delta t_i)^2 + \langle t_i \rangle^2) + \dots]$$

..... may be $b_i ((\Delta t_i)^3 + \langle t_i \rangle^3) + \text{higher orders}$

$$\Delta E \gg 0 \text{ or } \Delta E \ll 0 \iff \Delta t \gg 0 \text{ or } \Delta t \ll 0$$

Confining parallel spins within a box.

$$\Delta P \ll 0 \iff \Delta E \ll 0 \iff \Delta t \ll 0$$

Under a hard pressure or force, time could be returned.

All coefficients depend on medium and energies and thus, maybe, in some mediums, we have time returning and in some mediums, we don't have any change in time.

Figure 6: Near heavy cells, some time loops could be emerged. (a hypothesis)

The Urey-Miller experiment helps us to detect life holes.

Brane 1

Figure 7: The Urey-Miller experimental method is a way to detect quantum holes(a hypothesis)

Figure 8: The Montagnier method is a second way for detecting quantum life holes(a hypothesis)

III. Material and Method :

In this paper, similar to the Urey-Miller and also Montagnier experiments, we propose a method for trapping and detecting quantum holes (See Figure 9).

A. Material:

1. 1000x microscope 2. Extra lens 3. Electrodes 4. Battery or Generator 5. a metal-glass slide 6. Heater and Cooler 7. Leaf 8. Bird embryos

B. Method:

1. We cut a leaf into several parts and again produce many small pores in them.
2. We build a metal-glass slide.
3. The slide should be connected to a heater from one side and a cooler from other side such as there be a possibility for producing sudden thermal change on it.
4. Two electrodes should be connected to a generator under the slide such any desired current and wave could be emitted.
5. Parts of leaf which includes pore should be put on the slide and under the microscope.
6. Waves and sudden changes in temperatures should be applied. Sometimes with each other and sometimes separately.
7. Leaf should be replaced by embryonic heart and its vessels. It should be alive.
8. Again sudden changes in temperature and waves should be applied

Figure 9: Some new methods for detecting life quantum holes(a hypothesis)

IV: Results:

5. Sudden changes in temperature and wave cause that some fluctuations in space-time occurs.
6. In these fluctuations, some quantum holes could be trapped and decay to life molecules or time loops.
7. In figure 10, we present a time loop near blood vessels of a bird embryonic heart. We have taken related video. We can observe that events in 7th and 18th seconds are approximately the same. For example, three molecules are coming down and although, there is a separation in time of two events, however, it seems that one scene is repeating. Although, there are some differences so. These differences may be due to higher orders of time like third orders.
8. To clear events, we bring scenes of 7th and 18th seconds in figures 11 and 12 separately. It is clear that separation distance between three molecules and their motions are the same, however, their place changes minorly. However, this change isn't equal to expected change for this time period of time.
9. In figure 13, we have taken some signatures of a quantum hole on a leaf. In this experiment, some molecules are appearing, decay, vanish and again appears. This event occurred many times
10. In figure 14, some molecules move towards several points, disappear and some other molecules appear. This event also occurs many times.
11. These quantum holes may be trapped by chance. For example, maybe, in other experiment with similar conditions, we couldn't detect any.
12. The best times for doing these types of experiments are nights of winter.

Figure 10: A time loop for molecules near blood vessels of a bird embryo (a hypothesis)

Figure 11: Motions of molecules near bird embryonic vessels (7s) (a hypothesis)

Figure 12: Motions of molecules near bird embryonic vessels (18s) (a hypothesis)

Figure 13: Repeat of events in a time loop near a heavy object on the leaf (a hypothesis)

Figure 14: Disappearance of particles by quantum holes on the leaf (a hypothesis)

Discussion:

In previous sections, we proposed some signatures of life quantum hole. If this assumption be true, there is a relation between number of quantum holes and number of life molecules. This means that nature only produce special numbers of life molecules. Now, if we change conditions, what may be occurred (See Figure 15).

Suppose that by vaccinations, we induce extra genetic matters and life molecules into all bodies. Or, by towers, we produce extra waves.

1. These will change the number of life molecules. Consequently, some extra holes remain. These holes may decay and produce extra viruses or reversely, vanish present creatures.
2. A quantum hole could produce time loop on a cell. When this cell divides into two new cells, time may return minorly and new cell is emerged. This means that instead of two cells, we have three cells. This may be the origin of a tumor.

Figure 15: EM towers and vaccinations kill or produce some quantum holes and vanish some creatures. (a hypothesis)

Conclusion:

In this research, we show that near biological cells and under some conditions, like hard pressures, applying waves and sudden changes in temperatures, time seems to become non-linear, return and looped and some scenes seems to be repeated. This may be occurred by decaying some quantum life holes and generalizing uncertainty principle near cells. In fact, cells act like a detector for these holes. Because, DNAs within cells are built from spinors which by coiling, they become close to each other, produce very hard pressure and change space-time such as holes could be absorbed. These holes may be emerged within life clouds or come from other branes in the 11-dimensional world. The process of formation of holes could be considered in bio-cosmic model. In this model, our universe is located on a brane which interacts with other branes in extra dimension. In our brane, according to Abraham Loeb idea, after big bang, first waves and then particles are emerged. Next, particles join to each other and form atoms. Eventually, by decreasing temperature to 273-373 K, life molecules are emerged. These molecules may build initial cosmic clouds which divide into several parts. Each part could be compacted, surrounded by other molecules and form planets and stars. According to energy-matter conservation law, these compacted clouds may evolve and some of their matters convert to energy and quantum holes. Compactifications causes that nature of medium changes and GUP or non-linear time is emerged. Also, some holes may come out of other branes in extra dimensions. Maybe, life molecules in other branes are compacted in extra dimensions and emit some life holes. These holes could decay and produce life molecules and non-linear time. These molecules may join to each other and form viruses, bacteria, animals and plants. Number of holes and life molecules may be a constant. For this reason, by passing time and increasing number of creatures, their sizes become small. For example, initial dinosaurs disappear and present animals appear. Up to date, the Urey-Miller lab and Montagnier group have observed the emergence of life molecules by waves which may confirm this hypothesis. Motivated by those observations, we did some experiments for taking these holes near plant and bird embryonic cells and observed some signatures of time loop and GUP.

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